

Agroforestry in Viticulture

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Trees scattered within vineyard rows in a Mediterranean climate

Agroforestry in viticulture, also known as vitiforestry, is an ancient practice of integrating tree cultivation or forestry with vine growing. This integration of trees into a viticulture system can take various forms. The four main methods are:

- Hedgerows at the edges of plots or between vineyard blocks.
- Rows of trees interspersed between vine rows.
- Isolated trees within the vine rows.
- "Vigne mariée": rows of trees within the vine row acting as trellises.

The choice of tree species will depend on the pedoclimatic context, specific issues of the plot, potential production goals, and the type of spatial layout.

In addition to the ecosystem services typically provided by trees (e.g. soil fertility, water cycle, windbreaks, microclimate), vitiforestry is also a natural method of pest control against the grapevine moth by allowing bats, which are predators of the adult stage of this pest, to enter the vineyards.

For rows of trees between vine rows, it is important to properly calculate the required spacing to allow for machine passage according to the planned technical itinerary. Likewise, if fruit trees are planted, sufficient space must be allocated to avoid interfering with harvests.

Agroforestry plots can benefit from agricultural subsidies under the first pillar of the CAP, provided that no more than 100 trees per hectare are planted. Vineyards located between two rows of trees must have a minimum area of 0.1 ha. When declaring harvests, the area covered by tree rows must be subtracted from the area planted with vines.

However, it is important to note that the specifications of certain designations (IGP, AOC) require specific management practices, such as a minimum number of vine plants per hectare or monoculture of vine varieties.

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